

Non-thermal plasma assisted methane oxidation inside a DBD reactor: Effect of monometallic catalyst on energy efficiency and CO₂ selectivity

Abhinash Kumar Singh^{a,b,*}, Jasmiina Palo^a, Johanna Kihlman^a, Tiina Heikola^a, Mika Suvanto^b, Pekka Simell^a, Niko M. Kinnunen^b

^a VTT, Technical Research Centre of Finland, Tietotie 4, 02150 Espoo, Finland

^b University of Eastern Finland, Department of Chemistry and Sustainable Technology, Yliopistokatu 7, 80130 Joensuu, Finland

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ABSTRACT

The oxidation of methane was studied in a co-axial dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) quartz tube reactor at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. Methane oxidation was investigated in two reactor configurations: an empty DBD reactor and a packed-bed DBD reactor containing various oxidation catalysts (Co/Al₂O₃, Cu/Al₂O₃, Fe/Al₂O₃, Pt/Al₂O₃, and Pd/Al₂O₃). Methane oxidation was examined at plasma power levels ranging from 20 to 40 W. In the empty DBD reactor, methane conversion was initiated at 23 W plasma power. Methane conversion increased with increasing plasma power due to generation of more active species. The main methane oxidation products were CO and CO₂. Both CO₂ selectivity and energy efficiency improved with increasing plasma power. However, methane conversion, CO₂ selectivity, and energy efficiency declined as the gas flow rate was increased due to the reduced residence time of gases inside the plasma discharge zone. In the packed-bed DBD reactor, methane conversion was lower than in the empty reactor due to the reduced residence time of gases inside the plasma discharge zone. The presence of catalyst increased the plasma power requirements for methane conversion. Among the catalysts, Co/Al₂O₃ and Cu/Al₂O₃ catalysts exhibited higher methane conversion at lower plasma power (<30 W), while Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst demonstrated higher methane conversion at higher plasma power (>35 W). The presence of catalysts generally improved CO₂ selectivity, with noble metal catalysts achieving above 95 % CO₂ selectivity across all plasma power levels studied. Despite the higher plasma power requirements in packed-bed DBD, both Pd/Al₂O₃ and Co/Al₂O₃ improved energy efficiency compared to the empty reactor.

1. Introduction

Methane (CH₄) is a significant greenhouse gas with a global warming potential 28 times greater than that of CO₂ over a 100-year period [1,2]. Anthropogenic (human-caused) sources constitute about 60 % while natural sources constitute about 40 % of total methane emissions [1]. One of the largest sources of anthropogenic methane emissions is cattle farming, which contributes to 14.5 % of total methane emissions [2]. In cattle farming, methane is produced through enteric fermentation and manure management [2]. The increasing concentration of methane originating from cattle farming requires urgent measures to combat climate change and global warming. Further, the concentration of methane in a cattle farm is relatively low (20–200 ppm), making both commercial utilization of methane and direct thermal combustion not viable [3]. Therefore, a novel technology that can achieve significant

conversion, is energy efficient, and is suitable for small dairy barns and cattle farms is required.

The oxidation of methane is a challenging task and poses several challenges. The overall oxidation of methane is an exothermic reaction ($\Delta H = -802$ kJ/mol), but the C–H bond is very stable and requires high energy ($\Delta H = 439$ kJ/mol) to dissociate [4–6]. To overcome the activation energy barrier, high temperatures between 700 and 1000 °C are used to achieve methane combustion, which makes the entire process highly energy intensive [7]. Such high temperatures pose another challenge in terms of catalyst deactivation due to coking [7]. Traditionally, noble metals such as palladium (Pd) and platinum (Pt) supported on alumina catalysts have been used to lower the activation energy due to their superior activity and selectivity [8–14]. The porous gamma alumina (γ -Al₂O₃) has a large surface area, good mechanical and chemical stability, and low cost which makes it an ideal support [15].

* Corresponding author at: VTT, Technical Research Centre of Finland, Tietotie 4, 02150 Espoo, Finland.

E-mail address: abhinash.singh@vtt.fi (A.K. Singh).

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However, noble metal-based catalysts are expensive and have limited availability, urging the need for cheaper alternatives [16]. Transition metal-based catalysts possess unique redox properties, allowing them to cycle between different oxidation states [17]. In addition, the presence of oxygen vacancies in these catalysts facilitates the storage and release of oxygen during reactions [17]. These benefits make transition metal-based catalysts, such as copper (Cu), cobalt (Co), and iron (Fe), suitable for methane oxidation and are being continuously explored for various oxidation studies [17–23].

Although catalysts can lower the methane activation temperature to 200 °C, the energy requirements remain unsuitable for practical applications in dairy barns. To overcome this challenge, non-thermal plasma (NTP) offers an innovative approach by activating methane at room temperatures and pressure. In NTP, high-energy electrons (1–10 eV) are produced which can partially ionize the gas containing highly reactive species such as radicals, ions, and excited species [18,24–26]. Since the mass of energetic electrons is small, the temperature of ions and electrons can be significantly higher than the overall gas temperature [12]. Hence, NTP is also called ‘cold plasma’ or ‘non-equilibrium plasma’ [12,18,25]. NTP can be generated by various methods, such as corona discharge, dielectric barrier discharge (DBD), and atmospheric pressure jets [12]. Among them, the DBD reactor offers several advantages, including high electron density, easy scalability, and lab-scale operation [27–29]. NTP produces highly reactive species that can undergo unfavourable chemical reactions at low temperatures and atmospheric pressure [29,30]. However, the reactions happening in NTP is difficult to control and can lead to the formation of undesired products [29–31]. The use of appropriate methane oxidation catalysts (MOCs) along with NTP can improve methane conversion and the selectivity of desired products [31,32]. Plasma and catalysts have strong interactions when combined, often resulting in synergetic effect [30–32]. Catalysts influence plasma discharge by enhancing electric field, changing discharge type, and helping form micro discharges in catalyst pores [32]. Similarly, plasma exposure affects catalysts properties by modifying its structure and morphology [32].

This study investigates the application of non-thermal plasma for methane oxidation at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. The impact of plasma power, feed flow rate, and catalysts inside a DBD reactor on methane oxidation, CO₂ selectivity, and energy efficiency was investigated. The goal is to develop a scalable and energy-efficient solution for methane oxidation suitable for small dairy barns and cattle farms.

2. Experimental

2.1. Catalyst preparation

Catalysts were prepared by incipient wetness vacuum impregnation method. The γ -Al₂O₃ Accusphere support (beads size 0.45–0.5 mm) was provided by Saint-Gobain. Noble metals such as palladium and platinum and transition metals such as copper, iron, and cobalt were supported on γ -alumina spheres (Table S1). In this process, the γ -Al₂O₃ spheres were first dried at 150 °C under vacuum of 50 mbar for two hours. Then, a solution of the respective metal precursor was impregnated on the γ -Al₂O₃ beads in de-ionised water. The maximal solution volume adsorbed by the beads was 1.16 mL per 1 g. After impregnation, the catalyst was dried in a rotavapor at 80 °C and vacuum of 50 mbar for at least 2 h or until the catalyst was completely dried. After drying, the catalysts were calcined in air at 500 °C for 8 h. The metal loading of 1 wt.-% was selected to serve as the baseline for comparing various catalysts under identical plasma conditions.

2.2. Characterization of catalysts

The specific surface area and porosity of the samples were measured using a nitrogen adsorption desorption technique with a Micromeritics

3Flex 3500 instrument at –196 °C. Before the measurement, a sample of 0.25 g was degassed at 200 °C for 16 h under vacuum. The surface area was determined by the multi-point Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method, while the porosity was evaluated using the Barret-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method.

The active metal loading of various catalysts prepared was determined by Inductively coupled plasma – optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) (5110 SVDV, Agilent Technologies). First, the solids were treated in a microwave (EthosUp, Milestone) with acid-assisted digestion method by weighing 0.2 g of the sample into microwave tubes. Then, 6 mL HCl (Suprapur 30 %, Merck), 3 mL HNO₃ (Empura 65 %, Merck), and 1 mL HF (Suprapur 30 %, Merck) were added to the tubes. Three microwave blank samples were included in the sample series. The tubes were closed and placed in a microwave digestion system. During digestion, the temperature was increased to 230 °C over 20 min and then maintained at 230 °C for 30 min. After the samples had cooled down, 10 mL ultrapure type 1 water (Synergy® UV Water Purification System, Merck Millipore) and 5 mL saturated H₃BO₃ solution (Emsure, Merck) were added. The tubes were closed and placed in the microwave system and the same method was run again. Prior to the analysis, the samples were diluted to 50 mL with ultrapure type 1 water (Synergy® UV Water Purification System, Merck Millipore) and filtered with syringe filters (0.45 μ m). The elements were analysed with ICP-OES instrument from 1/100 diluted and undiluted samples. Dilutions were made with 1 % nitric acid solution (Empura 65 %, Merck).

The morphology of the various catalysts was examined before and after the experiment by using Zeiss Merlin Schottky field emission gun scanning electron microscope (SEM), equipped with an Aztec EDS/EBSD energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS) with a silicon drift detector. The SEM images were taken between the working distance of 4 to 8 mm and at an acceleration voltage of 2 kV. The column mode was set to depth of field and probe current ranged between 40 and 60 pA. Both in-lens and secondary emissions detectors were used during imaging. Before measuring the elemental map, the SEM image was taken from selected area at a magnification of 100. A working distance of 10 mm and an acceleration voltage of 15 kV were applied. The column mode was switched from depth of field to analytical and the probe current was increased to 500 pA. The low-energy cutoff was set to 150 eV, and the high-energy cutoff to 20 eV. The elemental map was recorded in counts units. For better elemental mapping, the frame time was set to 30 s, with the number of frames set to infinity.

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of catalysts were performed in a Bruker AXS D8 Advance diffractometer with a Cu K α radiation. The catalyst was placed on top of the plastic background-free sample holder. Diffraction patterns were recorded with a 2 θ angular range of 15–90° at scanning rate of 0.02°/min. Step size of 10 s per step was employed in the measurement.

2.3. Activity measurement set up

A schematic representation of the experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1. It consists of a gas supply system, a coaxial DBD reactor, power supply system and the measurement system. The gas mixture of 0.99 % CH₄, 78.12 % N₂ and 20.89 % O₂ was provided by Woikoski Oy. The flow rate of feed gas was controlled by Bronkhorst mass flow controller (MFC). The methane concentration (1 vol.-% in air) was chosen to ensure a reliable signal for product detection with our analytical systems. Although the concentration is slightly higher than in typical dairy barns, it was selected to maintain analytical reliability and to enable meaningful comparison of catalyst performance across experimental conditions.

The DBD reactor consists of two coaxial quartz tubes. The outer quartz tube has an external diameter (ED) of 20 mm, an internal diameter (ID) of 18 mm, and a thickness of 2 mm. Similarly, the internal quartz tube has ED of 14 mm, ID of 12 mm, and a thickness of 2 mm. The discharge gap between the two coaxial quartz tubes is 2 mm. The DBD

Fig. 1. (a) Schematic diagram of the experimental set-up. Purple line indicates the gas flow lines, red and green line indicates electrical circuit of HV and ground electrode, respectively, and black line indicates electrical signals. (b) Front view of the packed-bed DBD reactor and (c) top view of the packed bed DBD reactor.

reactor is equipped with two electrodes separated by the quartz tubes, which serve as the dielectric barrier. A stainless-steel rod with a diameter of 11 mm is fitted inside the inner quartz tube, serving as the inner electrode. A stainless-steel mesh with a width of 20 mm encircles the outer quartz tube, acting as the ground electrode. The inner electrode is powered by a high-voltage (HV) supply, while the outer electrode is grounded with a 22 nF capacitor. The length of the plasma discharge zone was determined by the length of the outer ground electrode which was fixed at 2 cm for all the experiments.

In the packed bed dielectric barrier discharge (PB-DBD) reactor configuration, the catalysts were placed inside the plasma discharge zone for better catalyst and plasma interaction. This configuration is called 'in-plasma' configuration. The catalysts (450 to 500 μm in diameter) were placed on the top of quartz wool which was located outside the reactor's discharge zone. The quartz wool was employed to hold the catalyst bed in place. The weight of the catalyst used during this study was 1.11 ± 0.05 g (Table S1). The temperature of the catalyst bed was measured with a Fluke 62 Max infrared thermometer.

The plasma was ignited with PVM500–2500/DIDRIVE10 HV power supply with range from 10 to 300 W. The applied voltage was measured with a Tektronix P6015A 1000× probe, and the electrical current with a MAGNELAB High Frequency Current Transformer (HFCT). The electrical parameters were measured using TiePie Engineering Handyscope HS6 DIFF-oscilloscope. The oscilloscope was connected to a computer via USB cable which allowed the continuous measurements of four different channels. Channel 1 measured the voltage from HV electrode, channel 2 measured the voltage over the 22 nF capacitor, and channel 3 measured the current over the system. The data collected from the oscilloscope was used to calculate plasma power. The plasma input power can be calculated by measuring the area of Voltage-charge (V-Q) Lissajous diagram [33]. The average power dissipated can be calculated as shown in eq. 1.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Plasma Input Power (Watt)} &= \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T (U(t)I(t)) dt = \frac{1}{T} \oint (U(Q)dQ) \\ &= C_M f \oint (U(U_C)dU_C) = f \times S \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where U is the voltage, I is the current, T is the time, Q is the charge, C_M is the measuring capacitor, U_C is the voltage of measuring capacitor, f is frequency, and S is the area of Lissajous figure.

In our setup, plasma power was controlled by adjusting the voltage amplitude (VA1) and the resonance frequency. We varied VA1 across a frequency range from 26 kHz to 23 kHz. Lowering the frequency to 23 kHz resulted in more intense discharges, which led to higher methane conversion. However, the plasma became more unstable at this frequency. At the higher end (26 kHz), the discharge was more stable, but methane conversion decreased, when the same plasma power level was maintained. To balance plasma stability and methane conversion efficiency, we selected 24 kHz as the operating frequency for all activity tests.

The plasma power was generated by varying the voltage amplitude (VA1) between 20 % and 60 % at 24 kHz. Initially, the voltage amplitude was increased to 20 %, and the resonance frequency was fine tuned to obtain optimal plasma power. At each set voltage amplitude, the plasma power was allowed to achieve a steady state. It took approximately 30 min at each set point for both plasma power and the methane conversion to stabilize. The measurements were recorded only after stable plasma power and methane conversion was achieved. Then, the VA1 was gradually increased from 25 % to 60 % to achieve various plasma powers.

First, the experiments in the blank reactor were performed at different feed flow rates (1 vol.-% methane in air) of 200, 300, and 400 mL min⁻¹. Each flow rate experiment was performed on a separate day to ensure consistent operating conditions throughout an experiment. The experiments with catalysts were performed at a constant flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹, and the plasma power was generated as described above.

2.4. Gas analysis

The gaseous products and methane were analysed by online Agilent micro-gas chromatograph (490 µGC) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (Gasmeter FTIR Analyzer). FTIR was employed for the analysis of the gas products such as NO_x and N₂O. Although NO_x and N₂O was detected in our studies, their detailed analysis was beyond the scope of this study. Therefore, these findings are not discussed here but will be addressed in future work. The micro-GC was used for analysis of other gaseous products, including CH₄, O₂, N₂, CO₂, CO and H₂.

The methane conversion, product selectivity, carbon balance, and energy efficiency were calculated using following equations.

$$\text{CH}_4 \text{ conversion (\%)} = \frac{n\text{CH}_{4,\text{in}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right) - n\text{CH}_{4,\text{out}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right)}{n\text{CH}_{4,\text{in}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right)} \times 100\%, \quad (2)$$

where, $n\text{CH}_{4,\text{in}}$ is moles of methane introduced to the reactor and $n\text{CH}_{4,\text{out}}$ is moles of methane exiting the reactor.

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ selectivity (\%)} = \frac{n\text{CO}_{2,\text{out}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right)}{n\text{CH}_{4,\text{in}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right) - n\text{CH}_{4,\text{out}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right)} \times 100\%, \quad (3)$$

where, $n\text{CO}_{2,\text{out}}$ is moles of CO₂ produced during the experiment.

$$\text{CO selectivity (\%)} = \frac{n\text{CO}_{\text{out}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right)}{n\text{CH}_{4,\text{in}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right) - n\text{CH}_{4,\text{out}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right)} \times 100\%, \quad (4)$$

where, $n\text{CO}$ is moles of CO produced during the experiment.

$$\text{Carbon balance (\%)} = \frac{(n\text{CH}_{4,\text{out}} + n\text{CO}_{2,\text{out}} + n\text{CO}_{\text{out}}) \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right)}{n\text{CH}_{4,\text{in}} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right)} \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

The carbon balance across all set points in the different experiments ranged from 95 % to 105 %, indicating consistent and reliable gas-phase measurements. The carbon balance details are provided in supplementary material (Table S1).

$$\text{Energy efficiency} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{kJ}} \right) = \frac{\text{CO}_2 \text{ produced} \left(\frac{\text{mmol}}{\text{min}} \right)}{\text{Plasma input power (W)}} \times \frac{1000}{60} \quad (6)$$

The residence time of gases (τ) inside the plasma discharge zone is calculated as follows.

$$\text{Residence time } (\tau) = \frac{\text{active volume of the reactor (cm}^3\text{)}}{\text{total flow rate} \left(\frac{\text{cm}^3}{\text{min}} \right)} \times 60 \left(\frac{\text{s}}{\text{min}} \right) \quad (7)$$

The active volume of the reactor is defined as the volume of the plasma discharge zone or the region where plasma is generated. In an empty reactor, the entire discharge gap constitutes the active volume. However, in the packed-bed reactor, the active volume constitutes of the void space created due to the packing material. This void space determines the available region for plasma generation.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the results from N₂ physisorption and ICP-OES. There was not much difference between the catalysts and pure support. The 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst showed a slightly higher BET surface area (S_{BET}) of 263 m²/g than other catalysts (225–234 m²/g). Likewise, the pore volume and pore diameter were consistent across the catalysts. Notably, plasma exposure did not change the surface area and pore volume of the catalysts. All the spent catalysts were characterized and there was a minimal difference between the properties of fresh and spent catalysts (Table 1). It can be concluded that plasma did not have a significant effect on catalysts' physical properties or morphology. Due to the non-thermal nature of plasma, which consists of electrons with substantially higher temperatures than the overall gas. It's always suspected that these highly energetic electrons might lead to a change in surface properties during plasma exposure [34]. However, this was not observed in our studies.

Similarly, the metal loading of the catalysts was found to be close to the targeted weight percent. The preparation method was successful in achieving the desired catalyst composition. However, the 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃

Table 1
Physiochemical properties of fresh and spent γ -Al₂O₃ support and different catalysts prepared.

Samples	Fresh catalysts				Spent catalysts			
	N ₂ physisorption		ICP-OES		N ₂ physisorption		ICP-OES	
	BET surface area (m ² /g)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Average pore diameter (nm)	Active metal loading (%) ^a	BET surface area (m ² /g)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Average pore diameter (nm)	Active metal loading (%) ^a
γ -Al ₂ O ₃	231	0.61	10.5	–	233	0.59	10.1	–
1 % Co/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	231	0.61	10.5	0.89	226	0.60	10.6	0.96
1 % Cu/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	228	0.60	10.6	0.90	223	0.59	10.6	0.94
1 % Fe/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	231	0.60	10.5	0.92	227	0.60	10.6	0.88
1 % Pd/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	263	0.63	9.69	0.89	258	0.62	9.60	0.88
1 % Pt/ γ -Al ₂ O ₃	228	0.60	10.6	0.61	227	0.59	10.4	0.70

^a Targeted active metal loading was 1.00 wt.-% for each metal.

catalyst showed the highest difference between targeted and actual metal loading. Additionally, the analysis of fresh and spent catalysts showed negligible variations in elemental composition (Table 1). The elemental composition of the catalyst remained unchanged at the end of the reaction in plasma within the DBD reactor, suggesting that no leaching or major decomposition of the catalyst occurred.

Fig. 2 shows the distribution of palladium on the alumina surface in the fresh 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst and detailed surface morphology at 100

and 500 magnifications. The SEM-EDS performed on the catalysts showed similar observations for all the catalysts tested. The morphology of fresh and spent catalysts was widely investigated. There was no difference in the topography of the catalyst surface and weight distribution of metals between fresh and spent catalysts. This was observed across all catalysts studied (Fig. S1). The uniformity in morphology and composition suggests that no significant surface degradation or morphological changes were induced on the alumina surfaces in the plasma

Fig. 2. (a) SEM images at 100 \times magnifications of fresh 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst (b) SEM images at 500 \times magnifications of fresh 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst (c) Pd distribution in fresh 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst.

experiments. The results from elemental mapping showed a uniform dispersion of the active metal species on the alumina supports.

Fig. 3 shows the XRD pattern of various catalysts, including pure γ - Al_2O_3 support across a 2θ range from 15° to 90° . There were four distinct peaks at $2\theta = 37^\circ$, 45° , 66° , and 85° in the pure γ - Al_2O_3 support, which are reported in the literature [35,36]. All the catalysts show these peaks, which might indicate that the catalysts retain the structure of γ - Al_2O_3 support. Among the catalysts, 1 % Fe/ Al_2O_3 , 1 % Co/ Al_2O_3 , 1 % Cu/ Al_2O_3 , and 1 % Pt/ Al_2O_3 did not show any additional peaks, suggesting that the active metal species were highly dispersed on the γ - Al_2O_3 support surface. In the 1 % Pd/ Al_2O_3 catalyst, we observed additional peaks at $2\theta = 34.5^\circ$ and 55° . These peaks are the result of the formation of PdO on the catalyst surface [37].

3.1. Effect of plasma input power and flow rate with empty DBD reactor

Methane oxidation experiments were conducted in an empty DBD reactor with different flow rates of feed gas (1 vol.-% methane in air) at varying plasma input powers. Fig. 4(a) shows the effect of plasma input power and different feed flow rates on methane conversion in an empty DBD reactor. At 20 W of input power, the plasma did not ignite, indicating that the applied power was insufficient to provide the necessary voltage and current for both ignition and sustaining the plasma. The methane conversion was initiated at 23 W plasma power, and 11 % methane conversion was achieved at a 200 mL min^{-1} gas flow rate. The methane conversion increased to 90 % when plasma power was increased to 31 W at a 200 mL min^{-1} gas flow rate. It can be concluded that the methane conversion increased as a function of increasing plasma power. The result is in line with the earlier studies and can be contributed to the formation of more active species at higher plasma power [24,29,34,38,39]. When the flow rate was increased, very low methane conversion was detected at 23 W plasma power. At 25 W

plasma power, the methane conversion decreased from 37 % to 16 % when the flow rate was increased from 200 mL min^{-1} to 400 mL min^{-1} . At a plasma power of 31 W, the methane conversion decreased from 90 % to 56 % when the flow rate was doubled from 200 mL min^{-1} to 400 mL min^{-1} . It is evident that an increase in gas flow rate decreased the methane conversion. The decrease in methane conversion with an increase in total flow rate can be attributed to the reduced residence time of gases within the plasma discharge zone [40–43]. A shorter residence time inside the plasma discharge zone restricts the time for which methane molecules interact with energetic species such as electrons and radicals [40–43]. This reduces the probability of successful collisions, which results in lower methane conversion [40–43].

Fig. 4(b) shows the effect of plasma input power and the feed gas flow rate on CO_2 selectivity in an empty DBD reactor. The microGC and FTIR measurement showed that CO and CO_2 were the only products formed in the experiments. At lower plasma power, the selectivity of CO was higher than the selectivity of CO_2 . As the plasma power increases, the selectivity of CO_2 improves regardless of the flow rate. At plasma power of 23 W, the CO_2 selectivity was 35 % when the feed gas flow rate was 200 mL min^{-1} . At 25 W plasma power, the CO_2 selectivity increased from 23 % to 41 % when the flow rate was decreased from 400 mL min^{-1} to 200 mL min^{-1} . Similarly, at a plasma power of 31 W, the CO_2 selectivity increased from 37 % to 57 % when the flow rate was decreased from 400 mL min^{-1} to 200 mL min^{-1} . While the CO_2 selectivity decreased, the CO selectivity followed the opposite trend and increased with increase in gas flow rate. As mentioned above, the decrease in flow rate increases the residence time, which enables efficient interaction between methane and oxygen molecules, favouring complete oxidation of methane over partial oxidation of methane [24,41]. Additionally, longer residence time improves the chances of secondary reactions, such as gas phase oxidation of CO into CO_2 .

The non-thermal plasma generated by the DBD reactor activates both

Fig. 3. XRD patterns of different catalysts.

Fig. 4. Effect of plasma power and feed flow rate on (a) methane conversion, (b) CO₂ selectivity, and (c) energy efficiency in an empty reactor. Reaction conditions in the experiments were 1 vol.-% of CH₄, 21 vol.-% of O₂ and 78 vol.-% of N₂. Gas flow rate of the reaction gas was examined at 200, 300, and 400 mL min⁻¹.

methane and oxygen through electron impact dissociation, producing active species such as CH₃^{*}, H^{*}, and O^{*} radicals [44–46]. At ambient temperature and pressure, it has been reported that the reaction CH₄ + e⁻ → CH₃^{*} + H^{*} + e⁻ is mainly responsible for activating methane via

electron impact dissociation [7,15,47,48]. During the dissociation reaction, O^{*} atoms are produced as shown in the reaction O₂ + e⁻ → O^{*} + O^{*} + e⁻ which can further facilitate CH₄ oxidation through the reaction CH₄ + O^{*} → CH₃^{*} + OH^{*}. The OH^{*} radical can undergo another secondary reaction with methane to form water via the reaction CH₄ + OH^{*} → CH₃^{*} + H₂O [49]. The primary product inside the empty DBD reactor is CO because it is stable inside the non-thermal plasma [50]. The bond energy required to dissociate CO is slightly higher than the average electron energy inside a DBD reactor [50]. At higher plasma power, CO₂ can dissociate back into CO and O [50]. However, the presence of excess oxygen increases the amount of reactive oxygen species, which suppresses the formation of CO and increases the CO₂ selectivity with an increase in plasma power [50].

The energy efficiency is expressed in terms of micromoles of CO₂ produced per kilojoule of energy input (μmol/kJ). Fig. 4(c) shows the effect of total gas flow rate on the energy efficiency of an empty DBD reactor. The energy efficiency increases with an increase in plasma power for all flow rates. The energy efficiency is directly proportional to both CH₄ conversion and CO₂ selectivity. Both CH₄ conversion and CO₂ selectivity increases with increasing plasma power which improves the energy efficiency. Further, the increase in flow rate has a negative effect on the energy efficiency in the empty DBD reactor. As the total flow rate increases, the molar flow rate of CH₄ also increases. Hence, higher molar methane flow into the reactor should theoretically enhance energy efficiency. However, both CH₄ conversion and CO₂ selectivity decrease with increasing flow rate leading to lower energy efficiency. It appears that the positive effect of higher CH₄ molar flow rate cannot surpass the negative effect of lower CH₄ conversion and CO₂ selectivity. Hence, the energy efficiency at 200 mL min⁻¹ consistently outperforms the higher flow rate.

3.2. Effect of the catalyst on methane conversion, CO₂ selectivity, and energy efficiency

Fig. 5(a) illustrates the impact of various active metal catalysts supported on alumina on non-thermal plasma-assisted methane conversion inside the DBD reactor at a constant flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹. All the packed-bed DBD systems demonstrated lower methane conversion compared to the empty DBD reactor. Based on the methane conversion achieved at 30 W plasma power, the order of catalyst performance can be established as: 1 % Co/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Fe/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃. Transitional metal catalysts outperformed noble metal catalysts at lower and moderate plasma power. However, at higher plasma power, the order of catalyst performance changed, and the 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst achieved the highest methane conversion. In contrast, the 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃ catalyst showed the lowest methane conversion across all plasma power levels. Both Pd and Pt metals are considered highly active metals for low-temperature methane oxidation [14,51]. However, their behaviour in the DBD reactor differed significantly, likely due to differences in their chemical state on the alumina support. The 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst consists of both Pd and PdO phases, with PdO being responsible for methane oxidation [51]. In contrast, Pt in 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃ maintains its metallic form, even after calcination in air (oxygen) at 500 °C [14]. The metallic state of Pt can increase the conductivity of the catalysts [52]. The presence of conductive material in the discharge gap inhibits charge accumulation on the dielectric surface, resulting in a weaker electric field, lower electron energy, fewer reactive species, and lower methane conversion [52–54].

In an empty reactor, methane conversion was achieved even at a plasma power of 23 W. However, the presence of a catalyst inside the DBD reactor increased the required plasma power to ignite the plasma. Catalysts can act as dielectric material and increase the overall capacitance of the system [55]. Since the overall capacitance increases, the amount of charge that needs to be transferred across the catalyst bed increases, which leads to a weaker electric field compared to an empty

Fig. 5. (a) Methane conversion, (b) CO₂ selectivity, and (c) energy efficiency with increase in plasma power in different catalysts at constant flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹.

DBD reactor at the same applied voltage [53,55]. Bare alumina support exhibited the highest methane conversion at the lowest plasma power among the packed-bed DBD systems. The presence of active metals on the alumina support further increased the required plasma power to ignite the plasma or achieve even low methane conversion. The presence

of active metal on alumina support increases the conductivity of alumina support [52–54]. The presence of conductive material reduces surface charging and increases the breakdown voltage to ignite the plasma [53,54]. Hence, no methane conversion was achieved below 27 W when the active metal catalysts were introduced inside the plasma discharge zone.

The presence of a catalyst inside the discharge gap can influence the plasma parameters, such as breakdown voltage, discharge power, and the characteristics of discharges [53–56]. In an empty reactor, numerous filamentary microdischarges are formed, and the formation of microdischarges increases with an increase in plasma power [53,55]. In contrast, the presence of a catalyst inside the plasma discharge zone created weaker microdischarges and more surface discharges [53,55]. In addition, the electrical charges can become trapped between the catalyst particles instead of transferring from the high-voltage electrode to the ground electrode [55]. This phenomenon, known as partial discharging in packed-bed DBD reactors, reduces the intensity of the generated electric field, thereby limiting the efficiency of methane conversion [55].

Moreover, plasma formation depends on the volume of the chamber between the electrodes, known as the plasma discharge gap [57]. Introducing catalysts into this gap reduces the chamber volume, limiting plasma propagation [57]. Additionally, the presence of catalysts or support materials in the discharge zone significantly reduces gas residence time, as the available volume for gas flow decreases [58]. The presence of catalysts shortens gas residence time by 50–60 %, negatively affecting methane conversion across all tested catalysts and support materials. Overall, the PB-DBD systems showed lower methane conversion at higher plasma power compared to an empty DBD reactor due to the increase in the overall capacitance of the electric circuit, change in discharge properties, and reduced residence time of gases inside the DBD reactor.

Fig. 5(b) illustrates the selectivity of CO₂ in the presence of various catalysts inside the DBD reactor and at different plasma power and constant flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹. The presence of catalysts had significant effect on the CO₂ selectivity. Bare alumina support increased the CO₂ selectivity when compared to an empty reactor experiment. However, the CO₂ selectivity did not show any clear trend with increasing plasma power in the presence of alumina support. It has been reported earlier, that the CH₄ oxidation on γ -Al₂O₃ surface can be terminated by the formation of surface bidentate carbonate species [15]. These carbonate species are stable and cannot be converted into CO₂ (g) under mild conditions [15]. Hence, the γ -Al₂O₃ did not affect the CO₂ selectivity. All the active metal catalysts increased the selectivity of CO₂ when compared to pure alumina packed DBD reactor and empty reactor experiment illustrating strong plasma - catalyst synergy. The 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst showed 99 % CO₂ selectivity, while the 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃ catalyst showed over 95 % CO₂ selectivity across all plasma power levels. Similarly, both 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃ and 1 % Co/Al₂O₃ catalysts showed similar trend where the CO₂ selectivity increased when plasma power was increased from 27 W to 32 W. The order of CO₂ selectivity can be established as: 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Co/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Fe/Al₂O₃.

The active metal catalysts, particularly noble metal-based catalysts such as 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ and 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃, improve the decomposition of surface carbonates species into gaseous CO₂ [15]. The bidentate carbonate species can migrate from alumina surface to the active metal surface and desorb from the surface as gaseous CO₂ due to plasma-produced O atoms [15,59]. In addition, it appears that formation of hydroxyl (OH) group is critical for improved selectivity of CO₂ [59]. The presence of catalyst can stabilize hydroxyl radicals on the surface and prevent unwanted gas phase recombination reaction of hydroxyl radicals. The gaseous CO, and the adsorbed CO both can react with OH to form formate species which decomposes to give CO₂ gas [59,60]. It has been reported that methane reacts with adsorbed oxygen to form adsorbed carbonate and adsorbed formate which are intermediate

products to CO₂ and CO, respectively [61]. Hence, by stabilizing key intermediates and facilitating desorption of carbonates from the catalyst surface, the presence of catalysts enhanced CO₂ selectivity significantly.

Fig. 5(c) presents the energy efficiency, expressed in terms of micromoles of CO₂ produced per kilojoule of energy input ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{kJ}$), for both empty and packed bed DBD reactors at a constant flow rate of 200 mL min⁻¹. Catalysts that showed higher CH₄ conversion and CO₂ selectivity, such as 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃, 1 % Co/Al₂O₃, and 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃ demonstrated higher energy efficiency compared to empty reactor and alumina only catalyst. Although the 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃ catalyst showed the lowest methane conversion, it was slightly more energy efficient than the 1 % Fe/Al₂O₃ catalyst due to its higher CO₂ selectivity. The 1 % Fe/Al₂O₃ catalyst showed the lowest energy efficiency due to poor CH₄ conversion and CO₂ selectivity.

The energy efficiency of the 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst was 28 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{kJ}$, while that of the 1 % Co/Al₂O₃ catalyst was 23 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{kJ}$, both exceeding the 22 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{kJ}$ which was achieved energy efficiency of the empty reactor. The energy efficiency of 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃ catalyst was 21.5 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{kJ}$, which was close to the energy efficiency of empty DBD reactor. Even though the plasma power required for ignition in the packed bed DBD was higher than that of the empty reactor, the energy efficiency was better in the packed bed DBD reactor due to the presence of catalysts that promoted the formation of CO₂. The order of energy efficiency is: 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Co/Al₂O₃ > empty reactor > 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Pt/Al₂O₃ > 1 % Fe/Al₂O₃ > Al₂O₃.

4. Conclusion

In the present study, the complete oxidation of methane inside an empty DBD reactor and a reactor packed with various catalysts has been investigated. Methane conversion increased with increase in plasma power, achieving 90 % methane conversion in an empty DBD reactor at 31 W plasma power and 200 mL min⁻¹ gas flow rate. We observed that the only products inside an empty DBD reactor were CO and CO₂. The selectivity of CO₂ increased with increasing plasma power. The energy efficiency increased with increase in plasma power due to higher methane conversion and CO₂ selectivity. The increase in total feed flow rate reduced the residence time of gases inside the plasma discharge zone resulting in reduced methane conversion, CO₂ selectivity, and energy efficiency.

Among the catalysts, transitional metal-based catalysts such as 1 % Co/Al₂O₃ and 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃ demonstrated superior methane conversion at lower plasma power (<30 W) compared to noble metal-based catalysts. However, with increase in plasma power, the 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ catalyst exhibited the highest methane conversion. Furthermore, the presence of catalysts significantly improved the CO₂ selectivity compared to empty reactor and bare alumina support providing strong evidence for plasma catalyst synergy. In terms of energy efficiency, both 1 % Co/Al₂O₃ and 1 % Pd/Al₂O₃ showed higher energy efficiency than the empty DBD reactor while, the 1 % Cu/Al₂O₃ exhibited similar energy efficiency to the empty DBD reactor. Overall, these results highlight that PB-DBD reactors are effective in oxidation of methane into carbon dioxide, making them a suitable option for mitigating methane emissions originating from dairy barns and cattle farms.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Abhinash Kumar Singh: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jasmiina Palo:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Johanna Kihlman:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Tiina Heikola:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Mika Suvanto:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Pekka Simell:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Niko M. Kinnunen:** Writing – review &

editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.166610>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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